

Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean

Report on the Nature's Contribution to People

VERSION 1.1

Acknowledgment: This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 2222.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is solely responsibility of the authors and it does not represent the view of the PRIMA Foundation.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17779424

Project Information

Project Title	Sustainable water storage and distribution in the Mediterranean		
Project Acronym	OurMED	Grant Agreement Number	2222
Program	PRIMA Section Management of Water 2022 under Horizon 2020		
Type of Action	Water IA – Innovation Actions		
Start Date	June 1, 2023	Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ), Germany		
Consortium	<p>Remote Sensing Solutions GmbH (RSS), Germany</p> <p>Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</p> <p>Global Omnium Idrica, SLU (IDRICA), Spain</p> <p>Euro-Mediterranean Information System on know-how in the Water sector (SEMIDE), France</p> <p>La Tour du Valat, (TdV), France</p> <p>Technical University of Crete (TUC), Greece</p> <p>Università di Parma (UNIPR), Italy</p> <p>University of Sassari (UNISS), Italy</p> <p>University of Naples Federico II (UNINA), Italy</p> <p>Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN), Jordan</p> <p>Living Planet Morocco (LPM), Morocco</p> <p>AgroInsider (AGRI), Portugal</p> <p>Higher School of Engineering of Medjez El Bab (ESIM), Tunisia</p> <p>Boğaziçi University (BU), Turkey</p>		

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D3.3	Deliverable Name	Report on the nature's contribution to people	
Work Package number	WP3	Work Package Title	Water and ecosystems governance and socio-economic assessment	
Due Date	Contractual	Nov 30, 2025	Actual	Dec 1, 2025
Version Number	1.1			
Deliverable Type	Report	Dissemination Level	Public	
Authors	Cem İskender AYDIN, Ipek Ronahi Gündüz, İrem Daloğlu Çetinkaya, Begüm Özkaynak			
Reviewer(s)	Seifeddine Jomaa			

Document History

Version	Date	Stage	Reviewed by
1.0	27/11/2025	First draft to Project Coordinator	Seifeddine Jomaa
1.1	01/12/2025	Formatting and editing	Amir Rouhani

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	10
1.1. Purpose	10
1.2. Motivation and research questions.....	10
1.3. IPBES and Nature’s Contribution to People Framework	12
1.3.1. Ecosystem Services.....	12
1.3.2. Nature’s contribution to people	14
2. Qualitative assessment of NCPs.....	21
2.1. Demo site descriptions.....	21
2.1.1. Demo Site 1: Germany (Bode Basin)	21
2.1.2. Demo Site 2: Greece (Agia Basin)	21
2.1.3. Demo Site 3: Italy (Arborea Basin).....	22
2.1.4. Demo Site 4: Jordan (Mujib River Basin)	22
2.1.5. Demo Site 5: Morocco (Sebou Basin).....	22
2.1.6. Demo Site 6: Spain (Jucar Basin).....	22
2.1.7. Demo Site 7: Tunisia (Medjerda Basin)	23
2.1.8. Demo Site 8: Türkiye (Konya Basin).....	23
2.2. Assessment results	23
2.2.1. Relevance to the sites	23
2.2.2. General Trends	27
2.2.3. Common issues and key drivers of change	28
2.3. Discussion	29
2.3.1. The Eroding Foundation of Well-being.....	29
2.3.2. Key Drivers and Trade-offs.....	29
2.3.3. Methodological Strengths and Limitations	29
2.3.4. Pathways for Transformation	30
2.4. Conclusion.....	30
3. NCP Assessment in Konya Closed Basin (KCB).....	31
3.1. Study Area and Methodology	31
3.2. Descriptive statistics.....	33
3.3. Perception of environmental issues	35

3.4. Assessment of NCP Importance and Perceived Impact of Loss	37
3.5. Willingness to Pay and Act.....	40
3.6. Institutional Trust and Governance	42
3.7. Conclusion.....	42
4. Conclusion	43
5. References.....	45
6. ANNEX – STANDARDIZED EXPERT SURVEY	47

List of Tables

Table 1. Assessment of relevance of NCPs to Demo Sites.	24
Table 2. Bid amounts asked in the household survey.....	40
Table 3. Acceptance rates of farmers for potential income loss due to conservation of the Lake Beyşehir.....	41

List of Figures

Figure 1. Ecosystem Services Framework and its relation to human well-being,	13
Figure 2. IPBES Conceptual Framework.....	15
Figure 3. Conceptual evolution of NCPs from ES.	17
Figure 4. List of NCPs and their categories.....	18
Figure 5. Trends in all relevant NCP categories for the eight demo sites.....	27
Figure 6. Konya Closed Basin.....	32
Figure 7. Lake Beyşehir.....	32
Figure 8. Participant distribution.	33
Figure 9. Descriptive statistics of household and farmer surveys.....	34
Figure 11. Life satisfaction and sense of belonging in Konya residents.....	34
Figure 12. Perception of environmental issues for households.....	35
Figure 13. Prioritization in the economy vs environmental protection dichotomy.	35
Figure 14. Perceptions and awareness of water levels in the Basin.	36
Figure 15. Problem perception and potential solutions.	36
Figure 16. Assessment of NCP importance.	38
Figure 17. The assessment of the impact of NCP loss.	39
Figure 18. Info card shown to respondents during the household survey.....	40
Figure 19. Survival function derived from the cumulative acceptance rates using the non-parametric Turnbull estimator.....	41
Figure 20. Trust in institutions in KCB.....	42

Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work Package
CO	Consortium
PU	Public
R	Report
O	Other
DEM	Demonstrator
PT	Platform
NbS	Nature-based solution
NCP	Nature's Contribution to People
IPBES	The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MA	Millenium Ecosystem Assessment
MED	Mediterranean
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
RSS	Remote Sensing Solutions GmbH
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València
IDRICA	Idrica
SEMIDE	Euro-Mediterranean Information System on know-how in the Water sector
TdV	La Tour du Valat
TUC	Technical University of Crete
UNIPR	Università di Parma
UNISS	University of Sassari
UNINA	University of Naples Federico II
RSCN	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature
LPM	Living Planet Morocco
AGRI	AgroInsider
ESIM	Higher School of Engineering of Medjez El Bab
BU	Boğaziçi University

Executive summary

The overall objective of the "Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean" (OurMED) project is to design and explore innovative and sustainable storage and distribution systems tightly integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale. This is achieved by the combination of scientific and local knowledge, emerging from new and long-lasting spaces for social learning among interdependent stakeholders, society actors and scientific researchers in eight local and one regional MED demo sites. OurMED calls for a transition from a mono-sectoral water management approach based on trade-offs, to equitable multi-sectoral and integrative management that addresses all water bodies' capabilities and needs towards sustainability.

This report aims to assess (quantitatively or qualitatively) the benefits provided by natural water resources and water-related ecosystems (termed as ecosystem services or nature's contribution to people) helps steer a better policy formation and governance mechanism toward a good quality of life balanced between the economic, social and environmental dimensions. Within this task, a comprehensive socio-economic valuation process incorporating both monetary and non-monetary values by using integrated valuation methods was conducted within the IPBES concept of Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) framework. The framework offers an inclusive method for assessing how nature supports life and livelihoods in ecosystems. In that regard, this deliverable aimed to assess the trends of 18 NCPs, identify key drivers of change, and highlight critical trade-offs and transformative actions required across critical agricultural catchments.

For the first part of the assessment, a standardized expert survey on eight catchments across the Mediterranean region was conducted in eight demo sites in the OurMED project, to gather qualitative assessments of NCP trends over the past decade. Our analysis revealed a widespread decline, particularly in regulating NCPs. This decline was mainly driven by agricultural intensification, urbanization, and climate change, resulting in important trade-offs where stable food production is threatening other NCPs. These findings emphasized the Mediterranean's acute vulnerability of agricultural areas relying on threatened water resources and demonstrate the urgent need for transformative adaptation pathways to secure the region's nature and human well-being. Reversing this trajectory requires urgent and concerted efforts to foster transformative change, moving from sectoral, production-focused management to integrated, sustainable stewardship of the rich natural heritage that defines this vital region.

For the second part, a large-N survey with households and farmers in Konya Closed Basin was conducted by BU, and aimed to have more detailed analysis on the interactions between nature and society, by investigating the willingness of residents and farmers in the Konya Closed Basin (KCB) to conserve Lake Beyşehir, in Turkey, by using a large-N survey. Households and farmers in the region recognize the critical link between nature and quality of life, expressing a genuine willingness to conserve nature for its instrumental, relational, and intrinsic values. Yet, effective conservation is currently hindered by institutional deficits, specifically a lack of trust between farmers and governance structures. Protecting Lake Beyşehir to ensure dignified livelihoods for both

human and non-human life requires a delicate balance: reducing water usage without causing economic harm. This necessitates a democratic, just transformation led by new, legitimate institutions that can reconcile agricultural production with nature conservation, ensuring all stakeholders contribute fairly to the solution.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose

The primary purpose of this report is to address critical knowledge gaps regarding the deterioration of natural water resources and ecosystems in the MED region. Despite being a biodiversity hotspot, this area faces severe anthropogenic pressures, necessitating a transformative approach to environmental governance. Leveraging the IPBES Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) framework, this assessment aims to conduct a comprehensive socio-economic valuation of ecosystem benefits. By integrating both monetary and non-monetary valuation methods, the assessment seeks to capture diverse trends and pressures in the eight different demo sites within the OurMED project.

This assessment operates on the hypothesis that coordinated, multi-site evaluations can effectively map NCP trends even in contexts where high-resolution monitoring data is fragmented. The findings are intended to steer policy formation toward a holistic balance of economic, social, and environmental dimensions. Ultimately, this work supports decision-makers in evaluating Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and contributes directly to achieving the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development targets, ensuring both the ecological integrity of the Mediterranean and the continued well-being of its dependent populations.

1.2. Motivation and research questions

The Mediterranean region occupies a paradoxical position in global ecology: it is simultaneously celebrated as a cradle of civilization and a biodiversity hotspot, yet it is increasingly identified as a "hotspot of changes" facing severe and accelerating environmental stress (Dean et al., 2024). This region, characterized by its unique climate and a millennia-long history of human-nature co-evolution, is currently under siege from a convergence of anthropogenic pressures. Ecosystems ranging from the pastoral lands of the hinterlands to the fragile coastal lagoons are becoming increasingly vulnerable to climate change, pollution, habitat destruction, and resource overexploitation (Lacoste et al., 2023; Dean et al., 2024). These cumulative pressures threaten not only the ecological integrity of the Mediterranean basin but also the well-being of the diverse populations that rely on its life-support systems. To address these challenges and steer policy toward sustainability, it is crucial to understand the complex interplay between nature and society through robust analytical frameworks.

The scientific framework for understanding the benefits humanity derives from nature has evolved significantly over the last two decades. The concept of Ecosystem Services (ES) was popularized by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005), which provided a foundational taxonomy categorizing these benefits into provisioning (e.g., food, water), regulating (e.g., climate regulation, water purification), cultural (e.g., spiritual, recreational), and supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling). This framework was pivotal in linking ecological health to human well-being, emphasizing that humans are integral parts of ecosystems and that a dynamic interaction exists between them.

However, to better embrace diverse worldviews and knowledge systems—particularly those of indigenous peoples and local communities—the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) evolved this concept into "Nature's Contributions to People" (NCPs). As defined in the IPBES Global Assessment Report (2019), the NCP framework encompasses "all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature... to people's quality of life." It organizes these contributions into 18 categories across three broad groups: regulating, material, and non-material contributions. This shift offers a more nuanced and culturally inclusive lens for assessment, recognizing that nature's value transcends purely economic or utilitarian metrics.

Global and regional assessments indicate that nature is deteriorating at unprecedented rates, with regulating and non-material NCPs declining in parallel with biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019, Cimatti et al., 2023). The IPBES Global Assessment Report concluded that nature is deteriorating worldwide at unprecedented rates, with grave impacts on people. It revealed that around 1 million animal and plant species are threatened of extinction, and 14 of the 18 categories of NCPs assessed have declined since 1970. This assessment concluded that the world is on an unsustainable path and that achieving sustainability goals requires "transformative changes across economic, social, political and technological factors" (IPBES, 2019).

Further spatially explicit global research has reinforced these findings. A recent study by Liu et al. (2023) produced the first spatially explicit global assessment of all 18 NCPs, finding that 11 of them declined between 1992 and 2018, primarily due to the loss of natural ecosystems. This research highlighted that while synergies among NCPs are more common than trade-offs, the relationships between regulating and material NCPs often involve trade-offs. For instance, increasing material contributions like food production can lead to a decrease in regulating contributions such as water quality regulation and habitat maintenance. Transitional climate areas, like many parts of the Mediterranean, were identified as particularly vulnerable, containing few NCPs and exhibiting strong trade-off relationships. Furthermore, specific Mediterranean ecosystems are witnessing declines in functionality due to resource exploitation and pollution, highlighting the urgent need for integrated conservation planning which accounts for these spatial discrepancies and cumulative pressures (Lacoste et al., 2023; O'Connor et al., 2021).

Despite these insights, significant knowledge gaps remain at regional and sub-regional levels. This report's hypothesis is that particularly when hi-resolution environmental monitoring is not available or fragmented, coordinated, multi-site assessments using a consistent methodology are effective to understanding NCP's trends in specific socio-ecological contexts, particularly in vulnerable hotspots like the Mediterranean region. Such research is crucial for developing place-based, effective management strategies and policies.

The first part of this assessment aims to address this gap by providing a multi-site assessment of the status and trends of all 18 NCPs across eight demonstration sites. Using an expert-based survey (with 24 experts), we:

1. Assess the perceived trends of NCPs over the past decade.

2. Identify the key drivers of change and the critical trade-offs between different NCPs.
3. Discuss the policy implications for addressing the challenges to develop transformative adaptation pathways to enhancing NCPs in intensively managed agroecosystems regions

The second part of this assessment aims to have more detailed analysis on the interactions between nature and society, by investigating the willingness of residents and farmers in the Konya Closed Basin (KCB) to conserve Lake Beyşehir, in Turkey, by using a large-N survey. Two main research questions are to be answered:

1. To what extent do farmers and households attribute importance to the NCPs provided by Lake Beyşehir and its surrounding ecosystem and why?
2. Are stakeholders ready to take action? Specifically:
 - Are farmers ready to switch to less water-intensive crops, even if it leads to a reduction in their income?
 - Are households ready to contribute to a fund for conserving the lake, including supporting farmers in making this transition

1.3. IPBES and Nature's Contribution to People Framework

The scientific frameworks connecting nature to humanity has evolved significantly over the last two decades. While the concept of Ecosystem Services (ES)—popularized by the 2005 Millennium Ecosystem Assessment—established a foundational link between ecological health and human well-being through categories like provisioning and regulating services, it has since been expanded. To better embrace diverse worldviews and indigenous knowledge, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) introduced "Nature's Contributions to People" (NCP). Defined in the 2019 Global Assessment, the NCP framework offers a more inclusive lens, organizing contributions into regulating, material, and non-material groups to recognize that nature's value transcends purely economic or utilitarian metrics. Accordingly, this report will first outline the foundational ecosystem services framework in Section 1.3.1. Subsequently, Section 1.3.2 will provide a detailed presentation of the IPBES NCP framework.

1.3.1. Ecosystem Services

The concept of ecosystem services serves as the primary scientific framework for understanding the intricate relationship between ecological systems and human well-being. This framework was comprehensively formalized by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA), a global initiative launched in 2001 to assess the consequences of ecosystem change. The MA defined ecosystem services simply as "the benefits people obtain from ecosystems" (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment [MA], 2005, p. v). This definition marked a paradigm shift in environmental policy, moving beyond intrinsic conservation values to emphasize the dependency of human prosperity, security, and health on the natural world.

The MA framework categorizes these benefits into four distinct functional groups, highlighting the diverse ways nature supports humanity: provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services. (See **Figure 1**)

Figure 1. Ecosystem Services Framework and its relation to human well-being.

Provisioning Services are perhaps the most tangible, representing the material products obtained directly from ecosystems. These include food (crops, livestock, capture fisheries, aquaculture, and wild foods), fiber (timber, cotton, wood fuel), fresh water, and genetic resources used for biochemicals and pharmaceuticals (MA, 2005). The assessment highlighted that while humans have substantially engineered ecosystems to increase the output of specific provisioning services, most notably food production, which increased by roughly two-and-a-half times between 1960 and 2000, this has often come at the cost of degrading other services (MA, 2005).

Regulating Services encompass the benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes. These are often invisible but critical services that maintain the stability of the biosphere. They include air quality maintenance, climate regulation (both global CO₂ sequestration and local temperature/precipitation regulation), water purification, disease regulation, and natural hazard protection (e.g., flood and storm mitigation by wetlands and mangroves). The MA (2005) noted that approximately 60% of the ecosystem services evaluated, including many regulating services like water purification and pest regulation, were being degraded or used unsustainably.

Cultural Services refer to the nonmaterial benefits people obtain from ecosystems through spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, recreation, and aesthetic experiences. Nature plays a central role in shaping cultural diversity, knowledge systems, and social relations. The framework recognizes that human cultures are strongly influenced by their environments, and conversely, cultural values shape how societies manage and interact with nature (MA, 2005).

Supporting Services differ from the other three categories in that their impacts on people are often indirect or occur over very long-time scales. These services are necessary for the production of all other ecosystem services. Examples include soil formation,

photosynthesis, primary production, nutrient cycling, and water cycling. Without these foundational processes, the provisioning, regulating, and cultural benefits humans rely upon would cease to exist (MA, 2005).

A critical innovation of the MA framework is its explicit linkage of these services to the constituents of human well-being (see **Figure 1**). The assessment posits that human well-being is composed of five key elements: the basic material for a good life (livelihoods, food, shelter), health (strength, feeling well, clean air/water), good social relations (social cohesion, mutual respect), security (safety from disasters, secure resource access), and freedom of choice and action (MA, 2005). The framework illustrates that these constituents are inextricably linked to the status of ecosystem services. For instance, the degradation of regulating services like disease regulation can directly undermine human health, while the loss of provisioning services can erode material security and social stability.

Furthermore, the MA framework emphasizes the dynamic interaction between humans and ecosystems. Humans act as drivers of change, both direct (e.g., land-use change, pollution) and indirect (e.g., demographic, economic), altering ecosystems and the flow of services they provide. These changes, in turn, feedback to affect human well-being, creating a complex coupled system. This holistic perspective underscores that protection of natural assets is not merely an environmental concern but a developmental imperative essential for poverty alleviation and long-term sustainability (MA, 2005).

1.3.2. Nature's contribution to people

The framework for understanding the relationship between humanity and the natural world has continued to evolve, moving towards more inclusive and pluralistic models. While the ecosystem services framework laid the groundwork for linking ecological functioning to human well-being, recent international initiatives have broadened this scope to better encompass diverse worldviews, particularly those of indigenous peoples and local communities, and to integrate insights from social sciences and humanities more effectively. This evolution is embodied in the concept of "Nature's Contributions to People" (NCP).

1.3.2.1. IPBES and its conceptual framework

The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) is an independent intergovernmental body established by States to strengthen the science-policy interface for biodiversity and ecosystem services for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, long-term human well-being and sustainable development. Functioning similarly to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) but for biodiversity, IPBES was established in 2012 to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and policy action at various scales (Díaz et al., 2015).

IPBES brings together expertise from various scientific disciplines to provide policy-relevant knowledge and promote the implementation of knowledge-based policies. Its work is organized into four main areas: assessments, policy support, capacity and knowledge building, and communication and outreach. A central achievement of the platform has been the development of a conceptual framework that provides a common language and structure for all its functions. This framework is a highly simplified model of

the complex interactions between the natural world and human societies (Díaz et al., 2015).

Figure 2. IPBES Conceptual Framework.

The IPBES Conceptual Framework is innovative in its explicit inclusion of diverse scientific disciplines (natural, social, and engineering sciences), diverse stakeholders (governments, international organizations, civil society), and, crucially, diverse knowledge systems (Western science, indigenous, and local knowledge). It identifies six primary interlinked elements:

- **Nature:** This refers to the natural world with an emphasis on the diversity of living organisms. It encompasses concepts from Western science such as biodiversity, ecosystems, and the biosphere, as well as holistic concepts from other knowledge systems, such as "Mother Earth" and "systems of life" (Díaz et al., 2015).
- **Nature's Contributions to People (NCP):** This element embodies all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature to people's quality of life. It includes ecosystem goods and services as well as concepts like "nature's gifts" (Díaz et al., 2018).

- **Anthropogenic Assets:** These are built infrastructure, health facilities, knowledge, technology, and financial assets. The framework highlights that a good life is often achieved through the co-production of benefits between nature and these anthropogenic assets (Díaz et al., 2015).
- **Institutions and Governance Systems:** These represent the ways societies organize themselves and their interactions with nature. They act as indirect drivers of change, influencing how people access, control, and value nature (Díaz et al., 2015).
- **Direct Drivers of Change:** These are natural or human-induced factors that directly affect nature, such as climate change, land-use change, pollution, and invasive species (IPBES, 2019).
- **Good Quality of Life:** This reflects the achievement of a fulfilled human life, varying across societies. It includes concepts like human well-being, "living in harmony with nature," and "living-well in balance and harmony with Mother Earth" (Díaz et al., 2015).

This framework allows for a comprehensive analysis of how institutional decisions affect direct drivers, which in turn alter nature and the flow of its contributions to people, ultimately impacting human quality of life.

1.3.2.2. NCP Framework

To operationalize the link between nature and quality of life within this broader conceptual framework, IPBES introduced the notion of "Nature's Contributions to People" (NCP). As defined by Díaz et al. (2018), NCP are "all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (diversity of organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to people's quality of life."

This concept builds upon the earlier "ecosystem services" approach popularized by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment but addresses some of its limitations. Specifically, the ecosystem services framework was often critiqued for being overly dominated by natural sciences and economics, framing the relationship between people and nature primarily as a stock-and-flow model of natural capital and economic benefits. This often failed to engage perspectives from the social sciences or the lived experiences of local practitioners and indigenous peoples (Díaz et al., 2018). The NCP framework aims to be more inclusive by recognizing that culture is not just a separate category of "cultural services" but permeates all links between people and nature. It explicitly acknowledges that the perception of what is a "benefit" or a "detriment" can depend heavily on cultural, temporal, and spatial contexts (Díaz et al., 2018). (See **Figure 3**)

Figure 3. Conceptual evolution of NCPs from ES.

The NCP framework operates through two complementary lenses: a generalizing perspective and a context-specific perspective. The context-specific perspective is typical of indigenous and local knowledge systems, where knowledge is not necessarily intended to be universally applicable but is deeply rooted in specific cultural and geographical settings. The generalizing perspective, typical of Western science and policy reporting, organizes NCP into 18 specific categories (Díaz et al., 2018).

There are 18 NCP categories grouped under three broad, overlapping headings: Regulating NCPs, Material NCPs, and Non-material NCPs. Unlike the ecosystem services classification, where categories were often treated as distinct compartments (provisioning, regulating, cultural, supporting), the NCP groups explicitly overlap, recognizing that a single contribution from nature often spans multiple dimensions (Díaz et al., 2018). (See **Figure 4**)

Figure 4. List of NCPs and their categories.

Regulating NCPs: These encompass the benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes. They correspond closely to the "regulating services" of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment but are viewed through a broader lens that includes cultural interpretations of these processes.

- *Definition:* Regulating NCPs involve functional and structural aspects of organisms and ecosystems that modify environmental conditions experienced by people or regulate the generation of material and non-material contributions (Díaz et al., 2018).
- *Examples:* This group includes critical processes such as climate regulation (NCP 4), where ecosystems sequester carbon and regulate local temperatures and precipitation. It includes pollination and dispersal of seeds (NCP 2), which are essential for food production and the maintenance of biodiversity. Other categories include the regulation of air quality (NCP 3), ocean acidification (NCP 5), freshwater quantity and timing (NCP 6), freshwater and coastal water quality (NCP 7), and the formation and protection of soils (NCP 8).
- *Significance:* These contributions are often "invisible" until they are lost. For example, the regulation of hazards and extreme events (NCP 9) becomes starkly apparent when the loss of mangroves or coral reefs leads to increased vulnerability to storm surges (IPBES, 2019). The framework acknowledges that these regulating functions underpin both the material goods we consume and the non-material experiences we value.

Non-material NCPs: These refer to contributions that support mental and spiritual well-being, such as cultural identity and aesthetic experiences. This group significantly expands upon the "cultural ecosystem services" concept by emphasizing that culture is not an add-on but a central filter through which people relate to nature.

- *Definition:* Non-material NCPs are nature's effects on subjective or psychological aspects underpinning people's quality of life, both individually and collectively (Díaz et al., 2018).
- *Examples:* This includes learning and inspiration (NCP 15), where nature provides opportunities for scientific inquiry, artistic expression, and traditional knowledge transmission. It covers physical and psychological experiences (NCP 16), such as recreation and the mental health benefits of being in nature. Crucially, it includes supporting identities (NCP 17), where specific landscapes, species, or ecosystems form the basis of spiritual, religious, or social cohesion experiences.
- *Significance:* The NCP framework highlights that non-material contributions are often inextricably linked with material ones. For instance, food is a material contribution, but the preparation and consumption of traditional foods are deeply embedded in cultural identity and social relations (non-material). The loss of a species or landscape can therefore represent not just an economic loss, but a profound cultural severance (Díaz et al., 2015).

Material NCPs: These are tangible products like food, water, and raw materials. They correspond to the "provisioning services" of the earlier framework but are understood as co-produced by nature and human inputs (anthropogenic assets).

- *Definition:* Material contributions are substances, objects, or other material elements from nature that directly sustain people's physical existence and material assets (Díaz et al., 2018).
- *Examples:* This group includes food and feed (NCP 12), energy (NCP 11) such as biomass and hydropower, and materials and assistance (NCP 13) like timber and fibers. It also includes medicinal, biochemical, and genetic resources (NCP 14), which underpin both traditional medicine systems and the modern pharmaceutical industry (IPBES, 2019).
- *Significance:* While these are tangible goods, the NCP framework emphasizes that their availability is heavily mediated by institutions, technology, and human labor. Furthermore, the extraction of material NCPs often involves trade-offs with regulating and non-material NCPs. For instance, maximizing biomass energy production can compromise climate regulation or cultural landscapes (Díaz et al., 2018).

The 18th category, **maintenance of options** (NCP 18), spans all three groups. It refers to the capacity of ecosystems to keep future options open, preserving biodiversity and

genetic variability to allow for adaptation to unforeseen changes. This reflects the "option value" of biodiversity, acknowledging that we cannot fully predict what contributions future generations will need (Díaz et al., 2018).

In summary, the NCP framework represents a significant maturation of the science-policy interface. By categorizing contributions into Regulating, Material, and Non-material groups, while simultaneously acknowledging the fluid boundaries and cultural mediation of these categories, IPBES provides a robust tool for assessing the state of the planet. It allows for a global synthesis that is nonetheless sensitive to local contexts, ensuring that the voices of indigenous peoples and local communities are heard alongside those of western scientists in the effort to sustain the fabric of life on Earth.

2. Qualitative assessment of NCPs

To assess NCPs qualitatively, we utilized a standardized expert survey (see Annex) A detailed questionnaire was distributed to local experts and stakeholders at each demonstration site. For each of the 18 NCPs, experts were asked to assess:

- The relevance of the NCP to local water management and its context, supported by specific examples.
- The trend for the NCP over the last 10 years, rated on a simple “ameliorated, did not change, deteriorated” scale, accompanied by a detailed description of how and why the change has occurred.

The survey responses were synthesized and analysed for each NCP across all eight sites. Qualitative data on examples and drivers were analysed thematically to identify patterns and pressures.

2.1. Demo site descriptions

2.1.1. Demo Site 1: Germany (Bode Basin)

The Bode River Basin, situated in Germany, represents one of Central Europe's most comprehensively instrumented catchments and is integral to the TERENO project. Extending from the Harz Mountains in the southwest to the lowland plains in the northeast, this site encompasses the Rappbode Reservoir, Germany's largest freshwater reservoir, which supplies drinking water to approximately one million inhabitants. Historically, catchment management has relied on monosectoral approaches, segregating water allocation for domestic, agricultural, and ecosystem services. However, the prolonged drought conditions experienced between 2018 and 2021 have exposed the limitations of this fragmented strategy in addressing the basin's complex challenges.

2.1.2. Demo Site 2: Greece (Agia Basin)

The Agia karstic aquifer has been a primary source of drinking water for the Municipality of Chania since 1937, utilizing pumping wells and the Agios Ioannis aqueduct. Additionally, the Local Organization of Land Reclamation (TOEV) of Varypetro exploits karstic springs to irrigate adjacent agricultural lands. In the 1920s, the construction of a small dam to harness spring outflows and a tributary of the Keritis River for hydroelectric power led to the formation of the artificial Lake Agia. Although power generation ceased in 2008, the lake has evolved into a significant ecosystem supporting diverse flora and fauna. Nevertheless, anthropogenic interventions have introduced non-indigenous species, such as domestic waterfowl, goldfish, and the American bullfrog (*Lithobates catesbeianus*), which compete with native wildlife. As part of the Natura 2000 network (codes GR4340020 and GR4340006), Lake Agia is recognized as a vital habitat for European biodiversity conservation.

2.1.3. Demo Site 3: Italy (Arborea Basin)

Located in central-western Sardinia within the coastal Oristanese district, the Italian demonstration site lies downstream of the Tirso River. Prior to the 1920s, the Arborea plain was a malaria-infested swamp. Extensive land reclamation projects in the 1920s and 1930s radically altered the landscape, establishing new agricultural zones that have since defined the region's cultural and economic identity. Today, Arborea is among the most productive agricultural areas in Italy and Europe, underpinned by a robust cooperative system. Approximately 150 farms manage a herd of 30,000 dairy and 3,000 beef cattle across 6,000 irrigated hectares. This productivity highlights the essential role of water in sustaining the local economy. The district is bordered by wetlands protected under the Ramsar Convention, which constitute nearly half of Sardinia's wetland heritage. These ecosystems provide critical services while embodying significant cultural and historical value.

2.1.4. Demo Site 4: Jordan (Mujib River Basin)

Wadi Mujib, historically known as the Arnon Stream, is a river of significant regional importance. The Mujib River Basin, covering a drainage area of 6,571 km², is central to the area's ecosystem and water management. Characterized by a unique gorge formed through geological erosion, the basin includes the Mujib Dam reservoir, constructed in 2004. The region is noted for its archaeological ruins, rich biodiversity, and socio-economic relevance to local communities dependent on it for agriculture and freshwater.

2.1.5. Demo Site 5: Morocco (Sebou Basin)

Water management in the Sebou Basin has historically focused on large-scale hydraulic infrastructure, such as the Al Wahda and Idriss I dams, to meet agricultural, urban, and flood control needs. While these projects successfully increased water storage capacity, they often neglected ecological requirements, exacerbating habitat loss and water quality degradation from agricultural and industrial runoff. Increasing urbanization and agricultural intensification have further stressed water resources, resulting in groundwater depletion, salinization, and wetland reduction. Climate change has intensified these challenges through increased variability in precipitation and temperature, necessitating a shift from fragmented management to holistic, basin-wide strategies that integrate socio-economic and ecological priorities.

2.1.6. Demo Site 6: Spain (Jucar Basin)

Lake Albufera has undergone profound transformation due to both natural processes and human activity. Originally a brackish lagoon, it transitioned into a freshwater ecosystem over centuries of irrigation-based agriculture. Its open water surface has diminished from over 30,000 hectares in the Roman era to 2,433 hectares today, primarily due to sedimentation and conversion for rice cultivation. Since the mid-1970s, the lake has suffered from water quality degradation caused by untreated sewage and agrochemical runoff. Designated as a Natural Park in 1986 and included in the Natura 2000 Network, Lake Albufera faces ongoing challenges in restoring its ecological status and water quality.

2.1.7. Demo Site 7: Tunisia (Medjerda Basin)

The Medjerda River, shared between Tunisia and Algeria, generates over 1 billion cubic meters of surface water annually, irrigating approximately 55,000 hectares within the basin and additional areas via water transfer. The region receives average annual precipitation ranging from 350 to 1,500 mm. Over 70% of the watershed is dedicated to agriculture, predominantly rainfed cereals and fodder, with irrigated crops concentrated near reservoirs and the lower valley. Wooded and pastoral lands cover only about a quarter of the area, reflecting significant anthropogenic impact and declining natural vegetation. The river's morphology makes the downstream sections particularly vulnerable to flooding, posing risks to adjacent towns.

2.1.8. Demo Site 8: Türkiye (Konya Basin)

The Konya Basin confronts severe environmental challenges, notably groundwater depletion and soil salinization. Conflicts among stakeholders regarding water management have intensified in recent years. The proliferation of illegal wells has accelerated aquifer depletion, threatening both environmental integrity and agricultural sustainability. Current efforts aim to improve water distribution, irrigation planning, and crop selection to mitigate these pressing issues.

2.2. Assessment results

2.2.1. Relevance to the sites

The assessment of Nature's Contributions to People (NCPs) across the eight demonstration sites reveals a high degree of relevance for regulating, material, and non-material contributions, albeit with notable variations driven by local ecological, agricultural, and socio-economic contexts. See **Table 1** below, for a summary.

Table 1. Assessment of relevance of NCPs to Demo Sites.

		Demo Site 1: Germany	Demo Site 2: Greece	Demo Site 3: Italy	Demo Site 4: Jordan	Demo Site 5: Morocco	Demo Site 6: Spain	Demo Site 7: Tunisia	Demo Site 8: Turkey
		Bode	Agia	Arborea	Mujib River	Sabou Basin	Jucar Basin	MedJerda	Konya
1	Habitat Creation and Maintenance	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
2	Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules	Relevant	Relevant	Not relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Relevant
3	Regulation of air quality	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
4	Regulation of climate change	Relevant	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant
5	Regulation of ocean acidification	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Relevant	Not relevant
6	Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
7	Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
8	Formation, protection and decontamination of soil and sediments	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Not relevant	Relevant	Relevant
9	Regulation of hazards and extreme events	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Relevant
10	Regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes	Relevant	Limited relevance	Not relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Not relevant	Relevant	Relevant
11	Energy	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Relevant	Limited Relevance
12	Food and Feed	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Not relevant	Relevant	Relevant
13	Materials, companionship and labor	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Relevant	Relevant
14	Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant	Limited Relevance	Not relevant	Relevant	Relevant
15	Learning and inspiration	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
16	Physical and psychological experiences	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
17	Supporting Identities	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant
18	Maintenance of options	Relevant	Limited relevance	Relevant	Relevant	Relevant	Limited Relevance	Relevant	Relevant

2.2.1.1. Regulating Contributions

Regulating NCPs were consistently identified as highly relevant across most sites, underscoring the critical role ecosystems play in maintaining environmental stability and water security. Some critical insights are as follows:

Habitat Creation and Maintenance (NCP1): This was relevant in all sites except Türkiye, highlighting the importance of biodiversity hotspots. For instance, Germany's Bode Basin includes the Harz National Park, a Natura 2000 site home to rare species like the Eurasian lynx. Similarly, wetlands in Italy's Arborea and Morocco's Sebou Basin serve as vital nurseries for fish and birds. However, in Türkiye's Konya Basin, habitat quality has deteriorated significantly due to water extraction and pollution.

Pollination and Seed Dispersal (NCP2): While relevant in most sites, the degree of importance varied. In Greece's Agia Lake, migratory birds play a key role in seed dispersal. In Morocco, pollinators are essential for fruit and oilseed crops. Conversely, in Italy and Spain, this NCP was deemed less relevant or limited due to the dominance of intensive agriculture or lack of natural habitat expansion areas.

Regulation of Air Quality (NCP3) and Climate (NCP4): These were generally relevant, particularly where forests and wetlands act as carbon sinks. In Germany, forests sequester CO_2 , while in Tunisia's Medjerda Basin, vegetation captures volatile organic compounds. However, in Italy, intensive dairy farming is a source of greenhouse gas emissions, presenting a trade-off.

Freshwater Quantity Regulation (NCP6): This is critical across all sites. Reservoirs in Germany and Morocco manage water storage, while the Mujib Dam in Jordan supports irrigation. In Tunisia, hydraulic structures regulate flow but have reduced marine regulation effects.

Water Quality Regulation (NCP7): This was universally relevant. In Germany, riparian zones filter pollutants; in Italy, vegetation belts mitigate agricultural runoff. In Spain, constructed wetlands in the Albufera site are specifically designed to remove nutrients and suspended solids, directly improving water quality.

Hazard Regulation (NCP9): This was relevant in most sites, with wetlands and riparian zones acting as buffers against floods in Greece, Jordan, and Morocco. In contrast, Germany reported limited relevance, as the basin is more prone to droughts than floods.

2.2.1.2. Material Contributions

Material NCPs, particularly food and water, are central to the socio-economic fabric of all sites but often drive environmental degradation. Some critical insights are as follows:

Energy (NCP11): Relevance varied significantly. In Greece, the Agia Lake was originally created for hydropower. In Tunisia, agricultural waste offers biofuel potential. However, in Spain and Italy, energy production from biomass was considered less relevant or limited to specific pilot projects.

Food and Feed (NCP12): This is a primary focus in all basins. Italy's Arborea district is a major dairy producer, while Greece's Agia Basin supports water-intensive crops like avocados. In Jordan and Morocco, agriculture is vital for food security but strains water resources. In Türkiye, irrigated crops are a primary source of food but contribute to groundwater depletion.

Genetic Resources (NCP14): This was relevant in sites with rich biodiversity or traditional practices. In Tunisia, medicinal plants are used locally, and in Jordan, diverse ecosystems harbor potential genetic resources. However, in Germany and Spain, this was considered of limited relevance to current water management.

2.2.1.3. Non-Material Contributions

Non-material NCPs, including cultural and educational values, are increasingly recognized as vital for community well-being and sustainable management. Some critical insights are as follows:

Learning and Inspiration (NCP15): This was relevant in almost all sites. The Bode Basin in Germany and Agia Lake in Greece serve as models for research and education. In Spain, the Tancat de la Pipa wetland has become a site for environmental education. In contrast, in Türkiye, while the lake inspires culture, its role in formal education was less emphasized.

Physical and Psychological Experiences (NCP16): Recreational activities like birdwatching and hiking are important in Germany, Greece, and Jordan. In Spain, constructed wetlands offer spaces for relaxation. In Türkiye, the lake is a destination for tourism, providing aesthetic enjoyment.

Supporting Identities (NCP17): This was highly relevant in sites with strong cultural ties to water. In Italy, the reclamation history of Arborea shapes local identity. In Jordan and Morocco, water bodies are central to cultural heritage. In Türkiye, Beyşehir Lake is deeply rooted in the town's history and spiritual practices.

In summary, the assessment demonstrates that while regulating and material NCPs are universally critical, their management often involves trade-offs. Non-material NCPs, though sometimes undervalued, play a crucial role in fostering community stewardship and resilience.

2.2.2. General Trends

A striking trend across the majority of the demo sites indicated the significant deterioration of regulating NCPs over the last decade, in contrast with more varied trends for material and non-material NCPs (Figure 5). This overall decline in regulating services is a clear signal of increasing environmental stress and reduced ecosystem capacity to deliver essential, often unperceived, benefits to people. The assessment revealed a consistent and widespread decline in this category (Table S1). For example, Habitat Creation and Maintenance (NCP1), a foundational service, has deteriorated in seven of the eight sites, with key examples including extensive forest dieback in Germany’s Bode Basin and wetland loss in Morocco’s Sebou Basin. This widespread habitat degradation was a primary driver of declines in Pollination and Seed Dispersal (NCP2), which has worsened in six sites due to habitat loss and increased pesticide use. Furthermore, the Regulation of Freshwater Quality (NCP7) and Formation and Protection of Soils (NCP8) were in a state of decline across most sites, with agricultural runoff and intensified land use being the primary drivers. This loss of ecosystem resilience is also evident in the weakened capacity for the Regulation of Hazards and Extreme Events (NCP9), a common theme in Germany, Greece, and Tunisia.

Over the past 10 Years, how did this NCP change?

		→	↓	↑								
		Not changed	Deteriorated	Ameliorated	Germany <i>Bode</i>	Greece <i>Agia</i>	Italy <i>Arborea</i>	Jordan <i>Mujib River</i>	Morocco <i>Sebou Basin</i>	Spain <i>Jucar Basin</i>	Tunisia <i>Medjerda Basin</i>	Turkey <i>Konya Basin</i>
Regulating	NCP1 Habitat Creation and Maintenance		↓	→	↓	↓	→	↓	↓	↑	→	↓
	NCP2 Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules		↓	→	↓	↓	→	→	↓	→	→	↓
	NCP3 Regulation of air quality		↓	↑	→	→	→	→	↓	↑	↓	↓
	NCP4 Regulation of climate change		↓	↓	→	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓
	NCP5 Regulation of ocean acidification		→		→				↓			↓
	NCP6 Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing		↓	↓	→	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓	↓
	NCP7 Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality		↓	→	→	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
	NCP8 Formation, protection and decontamination of soil and sediments		↓	→	→	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↓
	NCP9 Regulation of hazards and extreme events		↓	↓	→	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↑	↓
	NCP10 Regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes		↓	↓		↓	↓	↓	↓		→	↓
Material	NCP11 Energy		↑	↑	↑	→	→	→	→	↓	↑	
	NCP12 Food and Feed		↓	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑
	NCP13 Materials, companionship and labor		→		→	→	→	→	↓		↓	→
	NCP14 Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources		→						↓		↓	↓
Non-Material	NCP15 Learning and inspiration		↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	→	→	→
	NCP16 Physical and psychological experiences		↓	→	→	↑	↓	↓	↓	→	→	↓
	NCP17 Supporting Identities		↓	→	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	→	→
	NCP18 Maintenance of options		↓	↓	→	↑	↓	↓	↓	→	↓	→

Figure 5. Trends in all relevant NCP categories for the eight demo sites.

Trends for material contributions are more mixed, often highlighting significant trade-offs between production and environmental health. Energy (NCP11) has seen amelioration in five sites, largely due to an increased focus on renewable energy sources like small hydropower plants and biogas. In contrast, Food and Feed (NCP12) presents a more complex picture. While it has deteriorated in five sites due to pressing issues like water scarcity and soil degradation, it has actually improved in Italy and Türkiye. These

improvements, however, have come at the expense of other NCPs, demonstrating a clear trade-off where increased agricultural output directly contributes to the degradation of the regulating services that are essential for long-term sustainability (See supplementary material, S2).

In contrast to the pervasive decline in regulating services, some non-material contributions have improved over the past decade. This is most notable for Learning and Inspiration (NCP15), which has generally improved in five (Bode, Agia, Arborea, Mujib, and Sebou) of the eight demo sites. These positive changes are often the result of enhanced research and monitoring capabilities, as well as the growth of eco-tourism initiatives (as in the cases of Arborea and Mujib River) that foster a greater appreciation for and understanding of the natural environment. This suggests that while the functional aspects of these ecosystems are under threat, their value for education, recreation, and inspiration is increasingly being acknowledged and developed.

2.2.3. Common issues and key drivers of change

Despite their geographical, ecological and socio-economic differences, the demo sites share a set of common environmental challenges, largely driven by similar anthropogenic pressures. The qualitative analysis of expert responses identified several recurring drivers of change across all sites, as follows:

i. **Agricultural Intensification:** The most pervasive driver of environmental change across the basins is the intensification of agriculture. In Italy's Arborea Basin, an intensive dairy industry has led to significant nitrate pollution in groundwater. In Tunisia's Medjerda Basin and Türkiye's Konya Basin, the expansion of irrigated agriculture and the heavy use of fertilizers and pesticides have caused soil salinization, water pollution, and a decline in biodiversity. This pressure to maximize food production often comes at a high environmental cost, degrading the very natural resources upon which agriculture depends.

ii. **Water Scarcity and Mismanagement:** Over-exploitation of water resources is a critical issue in nearly all the southern Mediterranean sites. The Konya Basin (Türkiye) is marked by severe groundwater depletion due to legal and illegal wells. The Sebou Basin (Morocco) and Agia aquifer faces conflicts over water allocation between agriculture, domestic, and industrial/touristic uses. Even in the seemingly water-rich Bode Basin (Germany), prolonged droughts have put immense stress on water availability, leading to significant alterations in water quality (Kong et al., 2022; Musolff et al., 2024). These issues are compounded by aging infrastructure and fragmented governance structures, as highlighted in the descriptions for Morocco, Tunisia, and Greece.

iii. **Climate Change:** The impacts of climate change are an exacerbating factor across all sites. The expert assessments repeatedly mention increased frequency and intensity of droughts and floods. In Germany, climate-induced drought is directly linked to massive forest dieback. In Tunisia, decreasing precipitation is worsening water scarcity. In Greece, more frequent extreme events are reducing the retention capacity of Agia Lake. Climate change acts as a threat multiplier, worsening existing vulnerabilities and making sustainable management even more challenging.

iv. **Urbanization and Land-Use Change:** The expansion of urban areas and infrastructure development is another significant pressure. In the Sebou Basin, urbanization contributes

to habitat loss and pollution. In the Agia (Greece), agricultural land is being converted for urban construction and photovoltaic fields, altering the landscape and its ecological functions. This conversion often leads to the irreversible loss of productive agricultural land and critical habitats.

2.3. Discussion

2.3.1. The Eroding Foundation of Well-being

The results from the eight demo sites present a concerning narrative: the fundamental capacity of nature to provide regulating services is eroding across the region, in intensively managed agricultural land across a wide gradient of climatic and socio-economic conditions. The widespread deterioration of these NCPs is especially alarming. The reported decline in Habitat Creation and Maintenance (NCP1) in seven of the eight sites, from the forests of Germany's Bode Basin to the wetlands of Morocco's Sebou Basin, directly undermines biodiversity. This habitat loss, coupled with agricultural pressures, drives the decline in Freshwater Quality (NCP7) and Hazard Regulation (NCP9), threatening the sustainability of agriculture, the safety of communities, and the availability of clean water, cornerstones of life and economies in all eight basins. This analysis confirms that the river basins in the Mediterranean are hotspots of vulnerability, where global environmental changes are manifesting with acute intensity.

2.3.2. Key Drivers and Trade-offs

The improvement of material NCPs like Food and Feed (NCP12) in Arborea (Italy) and Konya Basin (Türkiye), juxtaposed with the steep decline of nearly all regulating NCPs in those areas, vividly illustrates the trade-offs inherent in current management paradigms. The pursuit of maximizing agricultural output has created a vicious cycle of groundwater depletion (Konya), soil degradation and reservoir siltation (Medjerda), and water pollution from nutrient loading (Arborea), undermining the very natural capital upon which production depends. Urbanization and infrastructure development, particularly in the Sebou and Agia basins, represent another major driver, leading to irreversible habitat loss and degrading the cultural and aesthetic landscapes that are central to non-material NCPs. These findings underscore the urgent need for integrated planning that moves beyond sectoral silos and accounts for the interconnectedness of all NCPs.

2.3.3. Methodological Strengths and Limitations

The use of a qualitative expert survey provided rich, context-specific insights that would be difficult to obtain through quantitative methods alone. This holistic and flexible approach, adaptable to diverse scales, effectively captured the perceptions and lived experiences of those most familiar with the local social-ecological systems, aligning with the IPBES's emphasis on incorporating diverse knowledge systems. However, this methodology has limitations. The findings are based on expert experiences, which can be subjective. While our standardized framework minimizes variability of responses, the results are not a substitute for quantitative biophysical monitoring. Rather, they serve as rapid, multi-site diagnostics to prioritize areas for detailed research and policy action, inspiring a sustainable future vision.

2.3.4. Pathways for Transformation

The trajectory of NCP decline revealed in this study is a clear signal that business-as-usual is not a sustainable option for intensively managed agricultural systems where water resources management is critical for their sustainability. Achieving regional sustainability goals requires transformative change (IPBES, 2019). Our findings point to several key leverage points for such change:

- **Reforming Harmful Subsidies:** The current economic incentives that encourage unsustainable water use and agricultural intensification must be reformed (Sundrum, 2024). Shifting subsidies toward practices that enhance regulating and non-material NCPs, such as agroecology, water conservation, and habitat restoration, is critical.
- **Integrated Governance:** Cross-sectoral approaches to governance are essential. Water, agriculture, energy, and tourism policies must be co-developed within an integrated landscape and seascape planning framework that explicitly manages trade-offs and seeks synergies among NCPs.
- **Strengthening Local Stewardship:** The positive expert assessment of the potential for interventions to improve NCPs underscores the value of site-specific options. Empowering local communities and recognizing their knowledge in the governance of natural resources can lead to more effective and equitable outcomes, particularly for non-material NCPs that are deeply rooted in local culture and identity (Belete et al., 2024; Denning, 2025).
- **Investing in Nature-Based Solutions:** The potential for sustainability projects to ameliorate NCPs, as reported by our experts, underscores the value of investing in nature-based solutions (Belete et al., 2024). Restoring wetlands and forests to enhance water regulation, implementing green infrastructure in urban areas, and creating well-managed protected areas can provide cost-effective, long-term benefits for both nature and people.

2.4. Conclusion

This multi-site provides one of the first coordinated, multi-site assessments of NCPs across the Mediterranean basin, revealing a widespread and severe pattern of decline. The erosion of regulating NCPs, often traded-off for short-term stability in material production, threatens the long-term ecological resilience and human well-being of the region. The trends we have identified are not merely environmental issues; they are fundamental challenges to the future of food security, water availability, cultural heritage, and economic prosperity in the Mediterranean. Reversing this trajectory requires urgent and concerted efforts to foster transformative change, moving from sectoral, production-focused management to integrated, sustainable stewardship of the rich natural heritage that defines this vital region.

3. NCP Assessment in Konya

Closed Basin (KCB)

The Konya Closed Basin (KCB) in central Turkey, known for its fertile soils and agricultural significance, constitutes a cornerstone in the country's agricultural production. Situated in a region with limited rainfall and lacking major rivers, the basin has historically been the subject of large-scale irrigation endeavours. In the early 20th century, one of Turkey's first extensive water transfer projects diverted water from Lake Beyşehir—Turkey's largest freshwater lake—to irrigate the basin's farmlands. More recently, other interbasin water transfer projects, such as the Mavi Tunnel bringing water from Göksu River, have been developed in the Basin to meet rising water demands. However, the shift towards more profitable but water-intensive crops like corn has intensified water scarcity leading to unsustainable groundwater extraction and growing pressure on water levels at Lake Beyşehir. Indeed, beyond its role in irrigation, the lake also sustains vital ecosystem services in the region, highlighting the complex challenges of balancing agricultural expansion with environmental sustainability in the Basin.

Against this background, this study investigates the willingness of residents and farmers in the Konya basin to support conservation measures in Lake Beyşehir, employing the IPBES Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) framework. Using a detailed face-to-face survey with a contingent valuation module with 947 respondents, representative of Lake's direct and indirect users in the region, we assess households' willingness to contribute financially through paying increased utility bills to compensate farmers' losses in their transition to less water-intensive crops. In parallel, in-depth interviews with 50 farmers explored their willingness to forgo a portion of their agricultural income to safeguard the lake. Both the survey and in-depth interviews examined participants' understanding of the diverse NCPs provided by the Lake Beyşehir ecosystem. Overall, by analysing the relationship between participants' understanding of NCPs and their willingness to engage in conservation efforts.

3.1. Study Area and Methodology

The KCB, located in central Turkey, is a vital agricultural hub, historically renowned for wheat production and increasingly for industrial activities intertwined with agriculture. The region faces significant water challenges due to limited precipitation and the absence of major rivers, necessitating large-scale irrigation. Over time, agricultural patterns have shifted towards more profitable but water-intensive crops like sugar beets, corn, sunflower, and potatoes, particularly since the 1960s and 2000s. Today, irrigation accounts for up to 90% of surface and groundwater usage in the basin. This intensive water use has led to severe over extraction and groundwater depletion, resulting in environmental crises such as the formation of sinkholes. Lake Beyşehir, Turkey's largest freshwater lake and an ecological hotspot, is under immense pressure from water depletion, threatening its critical role as a habitat for endangered and migratory species.

Figure 6. Konya Closed Basin.

Figure 7. Lake Beyşehir.

To understand the social dimensions of these ecological challenges, a mixed-methods approach was employed. A household survey was conducted in January 2025 with 947 participants, capturing a broad demographic cross-section of the region. In parallel, in-depth interviews were conducted with 50 farmers.

Figure 8. Participant distribution.

The study operationalized the IPBES NCP framework by presenting 17 specific NCPs individually to participants, avoiding predefined categories to capture nuanced perceptions. For each NCP, participants were asked to rate its importance and the extent to which its loss would affect their lives. This approach allowed for an assessment of perceived value beyond simple instrumental or non-instrumental dichotomies. Furthermore, the study explored the willingness of stakeholders to take concrete actions: specifically, whether farmers would switch to less water-intensive crops despite potential income loss, and whether households would contribute financially to a conservation fund.

3.2. Descriptive statistics

The household survey was conducted in January 2025 with 947 participants, capturing a broad demographic cross-section of the region. The gender distribution was nearly equal (51% female, 49% male), with a wide range of ages represented. Education levels varied, with a significant portion of respondents holding high school (40%) or higher education degrees. These participants were drawn from districts of Selçuklu, Meram, Karatay, Beyşehir, Seydişehir, and Çumra, ensuring geographic representation across the basin. The farmer demographic was predominantly male, with education levels primarily at the primary (38%) and high school (32%) levels, and a concentration in the 55-64 age bracket (44%). These participants were drawn from Beyşehir, Seydişehir, and Çumra. (See **Figure 9**)

Figure 9. Descriptive statistics of household and farmer surveys.

Furthermore, the study delved into residents' subjective connection to the region, revealing a profound sense of belonging and satisfaction. When surveyed about their life in Konya, a striking 84.9% of respondents expressed being satisfied or very satisfied with living in the city. This sentiment is reinforced by the high degree of belonging reported, with 84.5% of participants indicating they feel a sense of belonging or a very strong sense of belonging to Konya. Residents evaluated the city favourably across several dimensions, particularly praising its historical and touristic sites, where 64% found them very or extremely sufficient. Similarly, opportunities for outdoor activities and the city's nature and natural beauty were rated highly, with over half of the respondents finding them sufficient. While cultural and artistic activities received slightly lower ratings, the overall picture is one of a community deeply rooted in and appreciative of their local environment and heritage. This strong place attachment suggests that conservation efforts framed around preserving the region's natural and cultural identity may resonate strongly with the local population. (See **Figure 10**)

Figure 10. Life satisfaction and sense of belonging in Konya residents.

3.3. Perception of environmental issues

The results reveal a population deeply concerned about environmental threats. A significant majority of household respondents expressed concern about climate change and global environmental issues (44.8% concerned, 47.1% very concerned). This concern extends to local issues specific to Konya, such as air pollution, lake drying, and habitat loss, with 52.3% concerned and 36.0% very concerned. (See **Figure 11**)

Figure 11. Perception of environmental issues for households.

When asked to prioritize between the environment and the economy, the responses were relatively balanced but leaned towards environmental protection, with 35.3% stating the environment should definitely be prioritized, compared to 25.7% for the economy. (See **Figure 12**)

Figure 12. Prioritization in the economy vs environmental protection dichotomy.

Perceptions of water levels in Lake Beyşehir align with scientific data on depletion. An overwhelming 85% of households and 94% of farmers reported that water levels have dropped significantly over the past decade. The perceived causes of this decline differ

slightly between groups. Households identified climate change and increased agricultural irrigation as the primary drivers. Farmers, while also acknowledging climate change as the dominant factor, pointed to illegal water wells as a significant secondary cause, highlighting their awareness of unsustainable practices within the agricultural sector itself. (See **Figure 13**)

Have the water levels of lakes and groundwater in Konya changed over the past 10 years? If so, in which direction?

What are the two most important factor causing the decline in groundwater and surface water levels over the past 10 years?

Figure 13. Perceptions and awareness of water levels in the Basin.

There is a notable disconnect between the perceived urgency of the problem and the perceived efficacy of current management and civic engagement. A large portion of households (47.2%) and farmers (76%) disagreed that Konya citizens are given a sufficient voice in water management. Similarly, many felt that the people of Konya are not making enough effort to address these issues. Interestingly, there is strong support for infrastructure projects transferring water from other basins (84% of farmers agreed), but also for switching to closed irrigation systems (60.3% of households and 58.7% of farmers agreed), suggesting a openness to both supply-side and demand-side solutions. (See **Figure 14**)

To solve the water problem in the KCB ...

Figure 14. Problem perception and potential solutions.

3.4. Assessment of NCP Importance and Perceived Impact of Loss

Participants demonstrated a high awareness of the diverse contributions Lake Beyşehir provides. For households, NCPs such as "Habitat creation and maintenance," "Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing," and "Regulation of air quality" were rated as very important or important by over 80% of respondents. While material contributions like "Food and feed" and "Energy" were highly valued as expected, regulating and non-material contributions (e.g., "Physical and psychological experiences," "Learning and inspiration") were also valued with comparable importance. (See figure 15)

For farmers, the importance of NCPs was even more pronounced, reflecting their direct dependence on the ecosystem. "Habitat creation and maintenance" was rated as very important by 64.7% of farmers. Material contributions like "Food and feed" were critical (58% very important), but so were regulating services like "Regulation of freshwater quantity" (66% very important) and "Regulation of air quality" (66% very important). This shows that farmers recognize the lake not just as a water reservoir for irrigation, but as a complex ecosystem supporting their livelihoods and well-being in multifaceted ways. (See Figure 15)

Figure 15. Assessment of NCP importance.

The assessment of the impact of NCP loss further reinforced these findings. Households reported they would be strongly or very strongly affected by the loss of "Physical and psychological experiences" and "Regulation of air quality." Farmers expressed even higher vulnerability, with 80% stating they would be very strongly affected by the loss of "Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing," and 76% by the loss of "Habitat creation and maintenance." This acute sensitivity to ecosystem degradation highlights the precarious position of agricultural communities in the face of environmental change.

Figure 16. The assessment of the impact of NCP loss.

3.5. Willingness to Pay and Act

The study employed a contingent valuation method to assess households' willingness to pay (WTP) for a conservation project aimed at reducing water loss in irrigation canals, decreasing agricultural water demand, and raising the lake's water level. The proposed project included training for farmers, infrastructure investment, and incentives for growing less water-intensive crops. (See **Figure 17**)

Konya'da Beyşehir gölünü korumak için bir proje başlatılacak!

Bu proje kapsamında şu adımlar atılacak:

Su kullanım planlarının oluşturulması ve daha verimli su kullanımı için çiftçilere eğitimler verilecek

Üstü açık ve toprak zemini su kanallarında yaşanan su kaybını önlemek için daha verimli altyapı yatırımları yapılacaktır

Çiftçiler daha az su tüketen bitkiler yetiştirmek üzere teşvik edilecek

Damla sulama ve yağmurlama gibi modern sulama tekniklerine yatırım yapılacaktır

Göledeki su kalitesinin korunması adına tarımsal kimyasalların kullanımı sınırlandırılacaktır

Göledeki su kalitesinin korunması adına evsel ve endüstriyel atıkların göle ulaşması engellenecektir

Bu adımlardan sonra:

Sulama kanallarındaki su kaybı %30 seviyesinden %5'e düşecek

%30 Su kaybı
↓
%5

Sulama %25

Gölden karşılanan tarımsal su talebi %25 azalacak

Böylelikle göl derinliği 7 metreden 8 metreye yükselecektir.

↑
8m
7m
Göl Derinliği

Figure 17. Info card shown to respondents during the household survey.

Using a double-bounded referendum format with varying bid amounts (see **Table 2**), the study estimated a monthly average household WTP of €5.53. Aggregated at the provincial level using the non-parametric Turnbull estimator using a survival function (see **Figure 18**), this represents a potential economic pool of approximately €46.5 million (1.9 billion TL) per year dedicated to nature conservation. This substantial figure indicates a strong public mandate for protecting Lake Beyşehir and a readiness to share the financial burden of transition.

Table 2. Bid amounts asked in the household survey.

	Scheme A	Scheme B	Scheme C	Scheme D
Initial bid	1000 TL	500 TL	250 TL	125 TL
Follow up bid, if «YES»	2000 TL	1000 TL	500 TL	250 TL
Follow up bid, if «NO»	500 TL	250 TL	125 TL	62.5 TL
Group size	24.5%	25,9%	24.4%	25.2%

Figure 18. Survival function derived from the cumulative acceptance rates using the non-parametric Turnbull estimator.

Farmers were asked about their willingness to forgo a portion of their income to switch to less water-intensive crops. Remarkably, 68% of farmers expressed a willingness to accept some income loss to support the lake's protection (See **Table 3**)

Table 3. Acceptance rates of farmers for potential income loss due to conservation of the Lake Beyşehir.

Would you accept any losses in your income by changing your product pattern to support a project that would protect Lake Beyşehir?	
Yes	68%
No	32%

Income Loss	Acceptance Rate
0%	35%
5%	4%
10%	8%
15%	2%
20%	6%
25%	10%
30%	24%
20%	4%
50%	6%

The motivations behind farmers' willingness to act were rooted in instrumental, relational, and intrinsic values. Key drivers included an awareness of long-term necessity, responsibility towards future generations, and the protection of local identity and culture. Moral and spiritual motivations also played a role. Conversely, those unwilling to contribute cited distrust in institutions, livelihood constraints, and concerns about fairness as primary barriers. Specifically, distrust in the proper use of funds and the lack of guarantees that others would also contribute were significant deterrents.

3.6. Institutional Trust and Governance

The study highlighted a critical gap in institutional trust. When asked which institution would best implement water protection projects, the Konya Metropolitan Municipality received the highest confidence (31.7%), followed by State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) (19.1%). However, a significant portion of respondents expressed scepticism towards various levels of government and international organizations. The reasons for not contributing more to conservation efforts were dominated by budget constraints (limited budget), but distrust and concerns about the improper use of funds were also notable.

Figure 19. Trust in institutions in KCB.

This finding aligns with the broader context of the KCB, where fragmented management and a lack of effective institutions have historically hindered conservation. The study suggests that successful intervention requires not just financial resources but also the building of trust and the creation of legitimate, inclusive governance structures. The potential for a "democratic and just transformation process," as highlighted in the IPBES framework, relies on addressing these institutional deficits.

3.7. Conclusion

The assessment in the Konya Closed Basin demonstrates a clear recognition among both residents and farmers of the vital and diverse Nature's Contributions to People provided by Lake Beyşehir. The lake is valued not merely as an economic resource but as a central component of the region's ecological health, cultural identity, and future resilience. The willingness of households to pay for conservation and of farmers to modify their practices indicates a strong social foundation for transformative change.

However, realizing this potential requires navigating complex trade-offs and addressing deep-seated institutional challenges. The current trajectory of agricultural intensification and water depletion is unsustainable. Reversing this requires a shift from purely supply-side solutions (like interbasin transfers) to demand-side management (crop switching, efficient irrigation) supported by robust policy instruments. The study underscores the need for new, legitimate institutions that can foster trust, ensure fair burden-sharing, and facilitate a harmonious balance between agricultural production and nature conservation. By leveraging the high awareness and willingness to act identified in this study, policymakers can develop more effective, community-supported strategies for the sustainable management of the Konya Closed Basin.

4. Conclusion

This report has presented a comprehensive assessment of Nature's Contributions to People (NCPs) across key agricultural catchments in the Mediterranean region, employing the IPBES conceptual framework to bridge ecological data with socio-economic realities. By combining a broad, multi-site qualitative survey across eight diverse demonstration sites with an in-depth case study of the Konya Closed Basin in Türkiye, it has illuminated the critical state of the region's natural capital and the complex social dynamics underpinning its management.

The qualitative assessment across the eight demo sites reveals a concerning and widespread pattern of decline in regulating NCPs. From the Germany's Bode Basin to the of Morocco's Sebou Basin, essential services such as habitat maintenance, water quality regulation, and hazard mitigation are eroding. This degradation is primarily driven by the intensification of agriculture, urbanization, and the compounding effects of climate change. While material contributions like food and energy production have been maintained or even increased in some areas, this has often come at the direct expense of the regulating services that underpin long-term resilience. This trade-off trajectory is unsustainable, threatening the very foundation of food security and economic stability in the region. However, the assessment also highlighted a beacon of hope in the resilience of non-material NCPs, such as learning, inspiration, and cultural identity, which remain strong and offer a powerful leverage point for community engagement.

The detailed case study of the Konya Closed Basin further nuances these findings by demonstrating that local stakeholders are acutely aware of these challenges. Residents and farmers in Konya not only recognize the vital importance of Lake Beyşehir's diverse contributions, ranging from irrigation to cultural heritage, but are also willing to make significant sacrifices to protect them. The willingness of households to pay higher utility bills and of farmers to accept income losses for conservation indicates a strong, latent social mandate for environmental protection. This challenges the assumption that economic interests universally trump ecological concerns. However, the study also exposes a critical barrier: a deep-seated lack of trust in existing institutions. The disconnect between the willingness to act and the confidence in governance structures to deliver results is a major hurdle that must be overcome.

Synthesizing these findings, it is clear that technical solutions alone, such as infrastructure improvements or new crop varieties, are insufficient. Achieving a sustainable future for the Mediterranean's water resources requires a transformative shift in governance and management paradigms. We must move beyond fragmented, sectoral approaches that pit agricultural production against nature conservation. Instead, we need integrated, polycentric governance models that align with the holistic nature of NCPs.

This transformation entails three critical pathways. First, economic incentives must be realigned; harmful subsidies that drive over-extraction and pollution should be repurposed to support regenerative practices and the stewardship of regulating services. Second, governance must be democratized and made more inclusive. Building trust

requires transparent decision-making processes that empower local communities and farmers, ensuring their voices and knowledge are central to resource management. Finally, we must leverage the strong cultural and emotional connections people have with nature. By framing conservation not just as an ecological necessity but as a preservation of identity and heritage, we can mobilize broader societal support for the difficult transitions ahead.

In conclusion, the Mediterranean region stands at a crossroads. The current path leads to the continued erosion of the life-support systems upon which millions depend. However, the evidence presented here suggests that a different path is possible—one where agricultural productivity is balanced with ecological integrity, and where the diverse values of nature are recognized and protected. Realizing this vision requires urgent, concerted action to foster the transformative changes in policy, practice, and governance that will secure both our nature and our future.

5. References

- Belete, M. D., Richards, N., & Gehrels, A. (2024). Ecosystem services provision through nature-based solutions: A sustainable development pathway to environmental stewardship as evidenced in the Protecting Lake Hawassa Partnership in Ethiopia. *Socio-Ecological Practice Research*, 6(3), 331-345.
- Cimatti, M., Chaplin-Kramer, R., & Di Marco, M. (2023). The role of high-biodiversity regions in preserving Nature's Contributions to People. *Nature Sustainability*, 6, 1385–1393.
- Dean, G., Francioni, M., Toderi, M., López-i-Gelats, F., Trozzo, L., Rivera-Ferre, M. G., ... & D'Ottavio, P. (2024). Nature's contribution to people provided by pastoral systems across European, African, and Middle East Mediterranean countries: Trends, approaches and gaps. *Regional Environmental Change*, 24(77).
- Denning, G. (2025). Sustainable intensification of agriculture: the foundation for universal food security. *npj Sustainable Agriculture*, 3(1), 7
- Díaz, S., et al. (2018). Assessing nature's contributions to people. *Science*, 359(6373), 270–272.
- Díaz, S., et al. (2015). The IPBES conceptual framework—connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 14, 1-16.
- IPBES. (2019). *Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services*. S. Díaz, et al. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
- IPCC (2022) *Summary for Policymakers Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösckke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 3–33, doi:10.1017/9781009325844.001.
- Kong, X., Ghaffar, S., Determann, M., Friese, K., Jomaa, S., Mi, C., ... & Rode, M. (2022). Reservoir water quality deterioration due to deforestation emphasizes the indirect effects of global change. *Water research*, 221, 118721.
- Lacoste, É., Jones, A., Callier, M., Klein, J., Lagarde, F., & Derolez, V. (2023). A review of knowledge on the impacts of multiple anthropogenic pressures on the soft-bottom benthic ecosystem in Mediterranean coastal lagoons. *Estuaries and Coasts*, 46, 2190–2207.
- Liu, Y., et al. (2023). Global assessment of nature's contributions to people. *Science Bulletin*, 68, 424-435.

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. (2005). *Ecosystems and Human Well-being: Synthesis*. Island Press, Washington, DC.

Musolff, A., Tarasova, L., Rinke, K., & Ledesma, J. L. (2024). Forest dieback alters nutrient pathways in a temperate headwater catchment. *Hydrological Processes*, 38(10), e15308.

O'Connor, L. M. J., Pollock, L. J., Renaud, J., Verhagen, W., Verburg, P. H., Lavorel, S., Maiorano, L., & Thuiller, W. (2021). Balancing conservation priorities for nature and for people in Europe. *Science*, 372, 856–860.

Sundrum, A. (2024). Beneficial and Harmful Effects of Agricultural Industrialization. In: *Public Welfare-Oriented Production of Food*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-69040-6_5

6. ANNEX – STANDARDIZED EXPERT SURVEY

Partner Survey for the Assessment of Nature's Contribution to
People in OurMED Demo Sites

OurMED - Sustainable water storage and distribution in the Mediterranean.

Task 3.3. Assessment of the multiple benefits of nature

Boğaziçi University, Institute of Environmental Sciences

Istanbul, Turkey

INTRODUCTION

The following survey is conducted by Boğaziçi University team, as part of the **Task 3.3: Assessment of the multiple benefits of nature**. The objective of this task is to conduct a comprehensive socio-economic valuation process incorporating monetary and non-monetary values by using integrated valuation method to understand differences in valuation languages and multiplicity of worldviews held by stakeholders.

As part of this task, we are we going to assess Nature’s Contributions to People (NCPs) in all demo sites. «NCPs are all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (diversity of organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to people’s quality of life» (Diaz et al., 2018).¹ There is a total of 18 NCPs, categorized as material, non-material and regulating. The detailed information on NCPs is provided in the [guideline document](#).

For all questions and clarifications you may contact BU team (Ipek Ronahi Gündüz: ipek.gunduz@std.bogazici.edu.tr and Cem Iskender Aydın: cem.aydin@bogazici.edu.tr)

¹ Díaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Martín-López, B., Watson, R. T., Molnár, Z., ... Shirayama, Y. (2018). Assessing nature’s contributions to people. *Science*, 359(6373), 270–272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>

SECTION I.

Organization Name	
Demo Site Name	
Main Contact Person for Task3.3	<i>Please provide at least on contact person for future communications</i>
Short description of the demo site (max. 150 words)	<i>Please describe the historical evolution of the water management problem.</i>
Main issues in the demo site	
Contributors	<i>Please provide the names of the contributors</i>
Version no and date	<i>Start with V1, iterate at each revision. Write the date in YYYY.MM.DD format.</i>

SECTION II. ASSESSMENT OF NATURE’S CONTRIBUTION TO PEOPLE

NCP 1: Habitat Creation and Maintenance

The formation and continued production, by ecosystems or organisms within them, of ecological conditions necessary or favorable for living beings of direct or indirect importance to humans.

Examples: growing sites for plants, nesting, feeding, and mating sites for animals, resting and overwintering areas for migratory mammals, birds and butterflies, roosting places for agricultural pests and disease vectors, nurseries for juvenile stages of fish, habitat creation at different soil depths by invertebrates

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 2: Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules

Facilitation by animals of movement of pollen among flowers, and dispersal of seeds, larvae or spores of organisms beneficial or harmful to humans.

Examples: Pollination by bees, seed dispersal by birds, tropical plant seeds by fruit bats, ants moving spores, mosquito larvae dispersal

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 3: Regulation of air quality

Regulation (by impediment or facilitation) by ecosystems, of CO₂/O₂ balance, O₃, Sulphur oxide, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOC), particulates, aerosols, allergens. Filtration, fixation, degradation or storage of pollutants that directly affect human health or infrastructure

Examples: Pollutants filtered by wetlands, VOCs captured from air by urban green spaces, reduced aerosol and particulates by mangroves

<p>Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
<p>Please provide examples and short descriptions</p>			
<p>Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
<p>Please provide more information about the nature of change</p>			
<p>Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
<p>Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?</p>			

NCP 4: Regulation of climate change

Climate regulation by ecosystems (including regulation of global warming) through:

- Climate regulation by ecosystems (including regulation of global warming)
- Positive or negative effects on biophysical feedback from vegetation cover to atmosphere, such as those involving albedo, surface roughness, long-wave radiation, evapotranspiration (including moisture-recycling) and cloud formation
- Direct and indirect processes involving biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOC)
 Examples: Biological carbon storage and sequestration; methane emissions from wetlands, regulation of aerosols and aerosol precursors by terrestrial plants and phytoplankton

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 5: Regulation of ocean acidification

Regulation, by photosynthetic organisms (on land or in water), of atmospheric CO₂ concentrations and so seawater pH, which affects associated calcification processes by many marine organisms important to humans (such as corals)

Examples: Seagrasses, phytoplankton and coral reefs and algae absorb carbon and helps stabilizing pH levels, and algae produce oxygen

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 6: Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing

Regulation, by ecosystems, of the quantity, location and timing of the flow of surface and groundwater used for drinking, irrigation, transport, hydropower, and as the support of non-material contributions

Regulation of flow to water-dependent natural habitats that in turn positively or negatively affect people downstream, including via flooding (wetlands including ponds, rivers, lakes, swamps)

Modification of groundwater levels, which can ameliorate dryland salinization in unirrigated landscapes

Examples: wetlands provide flood control, forests allow rainwater to reach into the ground and recharge underground water, riparian zones filter out pollutants before water reaches the river and improve water quality for downstream users, mountain glaciers provide natural water storage

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 7: Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality

Regulation (by impediment or facilitation) by ecosystems, of CO₂/O₂ balance, O₃, sulphur oxide, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOC), particulates, aerosols, allergens. Filtration, fixation, degradation or storage of pollutants that directly affect human health or infrastructure

Examples: Wetlands filter natural water, vegetation in riparian buffers provides erosion control, coral reefs sustain ocean water clarity.

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 8: Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments

Formation and long-term maintenance of soil structure and processes by plants and soil organisms.

Examples: Physical protection of soil and sediments from erosion, and supply of organic matter and nutrients by vegetation; processes that underlie the continued fertility of soils important to humans (e.g. decomposition and nutrient cycling); filtration, fixation, attenuation or storage of chemical and biological pollutants (pathogens, toxics, excess nutrients) in soils and sediments

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 9: Regulation of hazards and extreme events

Amelioration, by ecosystems, of the impacts on humans or their infrastructure caused by e.g. floods, wind, storms, hurricanes, heat waves, tsunamis, high noise levels, fires, seawater intrusion, tidal waves; Reduction or increase, by ecosystems or particular organisms, of hazards like landslides, avalanches

Examples: Wetlands absorb excess floodwaters, reducing the impact of flooding; Mangrove forests act as natural barriers against storm surges and tidal waves, protecting coastal areas; Forests help stabilize soil, reducing the risk of landslides in hilly areas; Coral reefs dissipate wave energy, which helps protect shorelines from erosion and reduces the impacts of high winds and storms; Coastal dunes and vegetation help mitigate seawater intrusion by stabilizing sand and reducing saltwater encroachment into freshwater aquifers

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 10: Regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes

Regulation, by organisms, of pests, pathogens, predators or competitors that affect humans (materially and nonmaterially), or plants or animals of importance for humans. Also the direct detrimental effect of organisms on humans or their plants, animals or infrastructure

Examples: Regulation, by organisms, of pests, pathogens, predators or competitors that affect humans (materially and nonmaterially), or plants or animals of importance for humans. Also the direct detrimental effect of organisms on humans or their plants, animals or infrastructure

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 11: Energy

Production of biomass-based fuels, such as biofuel crops, animal waste, fuelwood, agricultural residue pellets, peat.

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 12: Food and Feed

Production of food from wild , managed, or domesticated organisms, such as fish, bushmeat and edible invertebrates, beef, poultry, game, dairy products, edible crops, wild plants, mushrooms, honey

Production of feed (forage and fodder) for domesticated animals (e.g. livestock, work and support animals, pets) or for aquaculture, from the same sources

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 13: Materials, companionship and labor

Production of materials derived from organisms in cultivated or wild ecosystems, for construction, clothing, printing, ornamental purposes (e.g. wood, peat, fibers, waxes, paper, resins, dyes, pearls, shells, coral branches)

Live organisms being directly used for decoration (i.e. ornamental plants, birds, fish in households and public spaces), company (e.g. pets), transport, and labor (including herding, searching, guidance, guarding)

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 14: Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources

Production of materials derived from organisms (plants, animals, fungi, microbes) used for medicinal, veterinary and pharmacological (e.g. poisonous, psychoactive) purposes. Production of genes and genetic information used for plant and animal breeding and biotechnology.

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 15: Learning and inspiration

Provision, by landscapes, seascapes, habitats or organisms, of opportunities for the development of the capabilities that allow humans to prosper through education, acquisition of knowledge and development of skills for well-being, information, and inspiration for art and technological design.

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 16: Physical and psychological experiences

Provision, by landscapes, seascapes, habitats or organisms, of opportunities for physically and psychologically beneficial activities, healing, relaxation, recreation, leisure, tourism and aesthetic enjoyment based on the close contact with nature

Examples: hiking, recreational hunting and fishing, birdwatching, snorkeling, diving, gardening

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 17: Supporting identities

Landscapes, seascapes, habitats or organisms being the basis for religious, spiritual, and social-cohesion experiences:

- Provisioning of opportunities by nature for people to develop a sense of place, belonging, rootedness or connectedness, associated with different entities of the living world
- Basis for narratives, rituals and celebrations provided by landscapes, seascapes, habitats, species or organisms
- Source of satisfaction derived from knowing that a particular landscape, seascape, habitat or species exists

Examples: Cultural, sacred and heritage landscapes, sounds, scents and sights associated with childhood experiences, iconic animals, trees or flowers

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			

NCP 18: Maintenance of options

Capacity of ecosystems, habitats, species or genotypes to keep options open in order to support a good quality of life.

Examples: Benefits (including those of future generations) associated with the continued existence of a wide variety of species, populations and genotypes. This includes their contributions to the resilience and resistance of ecosystem properties in the face of environmental change and variability. Future benefits (or threats) derived from keeping options open for yet unknown discoveries and unanticipated uses of particular organisms or ecosystems that already exist (e.g. New medicines or materials) Future benefits (or threats) that may be anticipated from ongoing biological evolution (e.g. adaptation to a warmer climate, to emergent diseases, development of resistance to antibiotics and other control agents by pathogens and weeds)

Is this NCP relevant to the water management issues on your demo site?	<input type="checkbox"/> Relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited relevance	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant
Please provide examples and short descriptions			
Over the past 10 years, how did this NCP change?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ameliorated	<input type="checkbox"/> Not changed	<input type="checkbox"/> Deteriorated
Please provide more information about the nature of change			
Can the project outcomes have the potential to ameliorate this NCP?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat likely	<input type="checkbox"/> Very likely
Please provide an explanation for how the project may or may not affect this NCP?			